

Viscometric studies of binary systems of *n*-decane with hexan-2-ol, heptan-2-ol and octan-2-ol at $T = 298.15$ K

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Manuscript received online 04 September 2012, revised 08 September 2012, accepted 27 September 2012

Abstract : This article reports experimental values of densities and viscosities on mixing of the binary mixtures of *n*-decane with hexan-2-ol, heptan-2-ol and octan-2-ol at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure, over the whole range of mixture composition. The corresponding excess and derived properties were computed from the experimental data. The results were fitted by means of the Redlich-Kister equation to estimate the binary coefficients and standard errors. The viscosities of all the mixtures were correlated by Grunberg-Nissan, Tamara and Kurata, Hind *et al.*, Katti and Chaudhari, Heric, Heric and Brewer and McAllister multi body model equations. The Prigogine-Flory-Patterson (PFP) theory and its applicability in predicting V_m^E is tested. The values of $\Delta \ln \eta$ have been analyzed using Bloomfield and Dewan model. Jouyban-Acree model is also used to correlate the experimental values of density and viscosity data. Experimental and computed results are discussed in terms of molecular interactions.

Keywords : Density, viscosity, *n*-decane, 2-alkanols, Bloomfield and Dewan model.

Introduction

Mixing properties, such as excess molar volume and deviation in viscosity have been used as a qualitative and quantitative guide to understand the molecular interactions between the components of the mixture, to develop new theoretical models, and also to carry out engineering applications in the process industry¹. Experimental liquid viscosities of pure hydrocarbon and their mixtures are needed for the design of chemical processes where heat and mass transfer and fluid mechanics are important². Also the petrochemical industry needs reliable viscosities for hydrocarbon mixtures to validate simulation programs and in the chemical industry, the information on the viscosity of liquid mixtures is necessary in different applications for surface facilities, pipeline systems, mass-transfer operations, etc.³.

Properties such as viscosity are required in many empirical equations for different operations such as mass and heat transfer processes. For example, it is necessary

to know the mass transfer coefficient to design gas-liquid contactors. To determine the equations that modelize the mass transfer process requires knowledge of the density, viscosity and surface tension of the liquid phase⁴. A survey of the literature⁵ showed that excess properties of binary mixtures of acetonitrile⁶, acetophenone⁷, methylbenzene⁸ and methylcyclohexane⁹ with alkan-2-ol have been reported earlier.

However, no attempt has been made to measure viscosities and excess molar volumes of binary mixtures *n*-decane with hexan-2-ol, heptan-2-ol and octan-2-ol at 298.15 K. We report here viscosities and densities of binary mixtures *n*-decane with hexan-2-ol, heptan-2-ol and octan-2-ol at 298.15 K. The measured data were used to calculate the viscosity deviations, excess molar Gibbs free energies of activation for flow and excess molar volumes. Variable-degree polynomials were adjusted to the results. The viscosities obtained were used to test the empirical relations of Grunberg-Nissan, Tamara and

Kurata, Hind *et al.*, Katti and Chaudhari, Heric, Heric and Brewer and McAllister multi body model equations.

Experimental

The sources and the mole fraction purities of the chemicals were : *n*-decane, S.D. Fine Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai (>99); hexan-2-ol, E. Merck (>99.6); heptan-2-ol, E. Merck (>99.7) and 2-octanol, E. Merck (>99.3). Prior to use all liquids were stored over 0.4 nm molecular sieves to reduce the water content and were degassed. The binary mixtures of varying composition were prepared by mass in special air-tight bottles. The masses were recorded on a Metler balance to an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ g. Care was taken to avoid evaporation and contamination during mixing. The estimated uncertainty in mole fraction was $< 1 \times 10^{-4}$.

The densities of the solutions were measured using a single capillary pycnometer made up of borosil glass with a bulb of 8 cm³ and capillary with internal diameter of 0.1 cm was chosen for the present work. The detailed pertaining to calibration, experimental set up and operational procedure has been previously described¹⁰⁻¹³. An average of triplicate measurement was taken in to account. The reproducibility of density measurement was $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5}$ g/cm³.

The dynamic viscosities were measured using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer⁹⁻¹³ calibrated with conductivity water. An electronic digital stop watch with readability of ± 0.01 s was used for the flow time measurements. At least three repetitions of each data reproducible to ± 0.05 s were obtained and the results were averaged. Since all flow times were greater than 300 s and capillary radius (0.1 mm) was far less than its length 50 to 60 mm, the kinetic energy and end corrections, respectively, were found to be negligible. The uncertainties in dynamic viscosities are of the order of ± 0.003 mPa.s.

The purity of the samples and accuracy of data were checked by comparing the measured densities and speeds of sound of the pure compounds with the literature values, which are given in Table 1¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Thus our results obtained are in good agreement with those listed in the literature.

The purity of samples was also checked by chromatographic method using HP 6890 FID detector, confirming

Table 1. Comparison of experimental densities (ρ), viscosities (η) and speeds of sound (u) of pure liquids with literature values at $T = 298.15$ K

Pure liquids	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)		η (mPa.s)	
	Expt.	Lit.	Expt.	Lit.
<i>n</i> -Decane	0.72635	0.7267 ^a	0.845	0.861 ^{b,c}
Hexane-2-ol	0.81084	0.8105 ^d	4.105	4.104 ^e
Heptane-2-ol	0.81374	0.81372 ^f	5.088	5.089 ^f
Octane-2-ol	0.81705	0.81708 ^g	6.429	6.435 ^g

^aRef. 14, ^bRef. 15, ^cRef. 16, ^dRef. 17, ^eRef. 5, ^fRef. 6, ^gRef. 7.

the absence of other significant compounds. The concentration of water was determined by Karl Fisher method.

Results

Experimental values of densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) of mixtures at 298.15 K are listed as a function of mole fraction in Table 2. The density values have been

Table 2. Densities (ρ), viscosities (η), excess molar volumes V^E and viscosities deviations $\Delta\eta$ of binary mixtures at $T = 298.15$ K

x_1	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$V^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	η (mPa.s)	$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + hexane-2-ol (2)				
0.0000	0.81084	0.000	4.105	0.000
0.0555	0.80294	0.135	3.569	-0.355
0.0999	0.79723	0.197	3.170	-0.609
0.1554	0.79050	0.267	2.725	-0.873
0.1998	0.78543	0.317	2.410	-1.044
0.2556	0.77942	0.372	2.062	-1.210
0.2999	0.77491	0.410	1.821	-1.306
0.3555	0.76955	0.448	1.561	-1.385
0.3998	0.76552	0.471	1.384	-1.417
0.4554	0.76072	0.490	1.198	-1.422
0.4998	0.75710	0.499	1.076	-1.400
0.5554	0.75279	0.499	0.952	-1.342
0.5997	0.74954	0.491	0.875	-1.275
0.6555	0.74566	0.470	0.802	-1.166
0.6999	0.74272	0.445	0.760	-1.063
0.7555	0.73925	0.402	0.725	-0.918
0.7998	0.73662	0.359	0.708	-0.790
0.8555	0.73348	0.292	0.699	-0.617
0.8999	0.73111	0.230	0.698	-0.473
0.9555	0.72829	0.138	0.703	-0.287
1.0000	0.72635	0.000	0.845	0.000
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + heptan-2-ol (2)				
0.0000	0.81374	0.000	5.080	0.000

Table-2 (contd.)

0.0552	0.80687	0.069	4.250	-0.596
0.0999	0.80155	0.120	3.732	-0.925
0.1555	0.79515	0.183	3.152	-1.269
0.1999	0.79026	0.229	2.740	-1.494
0.2554	0.78436	0.282	2.283	-1.715
0.2999	0.77983	0.319	1.962	-1.848
0.3554	0.77440	0.356	1.614	-1.961
0.3998	0.77024	0.378	1.375	-2.011
0.4555	0.76523	0.396	1.122	-2.029
0.4998	0.76141	0.401	0.954	-2.010
0.5555	0.75680	0.398	0.782	-1.946
0.5999	0.75327	0.386	0.673	-1.866
0.6554	0.74904	0.361	0.570	-1.734
0.6999	0.74579	0.333	0.510	-1.606
0.7553	0.74187	0.289	0.461	-1.420
0.8000	0.73884	0.246	0.440	-1.252
0.8555	0.73520	0.187	0.432	-1.025
0.8998	0.73239	0.135	0.438	-0.832
0.9553	0.72898	0.067	0.457	-0.577
1.0000	0.72635	0.000	0.845	0.000
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + octan-2-ol (2)				
0.0000	0.81705	0	6.429	0
0.0554	0.81077	0.036	5.222	-0.898
0.0998	0.80583	0.071	4.638	-1.234
0.1554	0.79974	0.119	3.972	-1.589
0.1999	0.79499	0.158	3.491	-1.822
0.2554	0.7892	0.205	2.951	-2.052
0.2999	0.78467	0.239	2.564	-2.19
0.3555	0.77916	0.275	2.136	-2.308
0.3998	0.7749	0.298	1.836	-2.361
0.4554	0.76969	0.318	1.509	-2.377
0.4999	0.76564	0.326	1.284	-2.354
0.5555	0.76074	0.326	1.046	-2.281
0.5998	0.75694	0.318	0.889	-2.191
0.6555	0.7523	0.298	0.73	-2.039
0.7000	0.7487	0.274	0.63	-1.89
0.7554	0.74432	0.236	0.538	-1.673
0.7998	0.74091	0.2	0.487	-1.476
0.8554	0.73674	0.149	0.45	-1.203
0.8999	0.73347	0.106	0.438	-0.966
0.9554	0.72948	0.052	0.445	-0.649
1.0000	0.72635	0	0.845	0

used to calculate excess molar volumes (V^E) using the following equation :

$$V_m^E \text{ (m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)} =$$

$$(x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2) / \rho_{12} - (x_1 M_1 / \rho_1) - (x_2 M_2 / \rho_2) \quad (1)$$

where ρ_{12} is the density of the mixture and x_1 , M_1 , ρ_1 , and x_2 , M_2 , ρ_2 are the mole fraction, the molecular weights, and the densities of pure components 1 and 2, respectively.

The viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) were calculated using

$$\Delta\eta \text{ (mPa.s)} = \eta_{12} - x_1 \eta_1 - x_2 \eta_2 \quad (2)$$

where η_{12} is the viscosity of the mixture and x_1 , x_2 and η_1 , η_2 are the mole fractions and the viscosities of pure components 1 and 2, respectively.

Excess Gibbs free energies of activation of viscous flow G^{*E} for binary mixtures can be calculated as

$$\Delta G^{*E} = RT [\ln (\eta v / \eta_2 v_2) - x_1 \ln (\eta_1 v_1 / \eta_2 v_2)] \quad (3)$$

where v is the molar volume of the mixture and v_i is the molar volume of the pure component, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, η is the dynamic viscosity of the mixture, respectively. η_i is the dynamic viscosity of the pure component i and x_1 the mole fraction in component.

The excess molar volumes and deviations in viscosity were fitted to Redlich Kister¹⁸ equation of the type

$$Y = x_1 x_2 \sum_i^n a_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (4)$$

where Y is either V^E , or $\Delta\eta$, and n is the degree of polynomial. Coefficients a_i was obtained by fitting eq. (5) to experimental results using a least-squares regression method. In each case, the optimum number of coefficients is ascertained from an examination of the variation in standard deviation (σ). σ was calculated using the relation

$$\sigma (Y) = \left[\frac{\sum (Y_{\text{exptl}} - Y_{\text{calcd}})^2}{N - n} \right]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where N is the number of data points and n is the number of coefficients. The calculated values of the coefficients a_i along with the standard deviations (σ) are given in Table 3.

Discussion

The variation in excess molar volumes, V_m^E with mole fraction of the binary mixtures of *n*-decane with hexan-2-ol, heptan-2-ol and octan-2-ol $T = 298.15$ are displayed in Fig. 1. The V_m^E curve for the mixture show positive deviation over the entire composition range.

Fig. 1. Plot of excess molar volumes (V_m^E) against mole fraction of *n*-decane with (O) hexane-2-ol; (□) heptane-2-ol and octane-2-ol (Δ) at $T = 298.15$ K. The corresponding dotted (---) curves have been derived from PFP theory.

Generally V_m^E can be considered as arising from three types of interactions between component molecules of liquid mixtures^{8,19-21}; (1) physical interactions consisting of mainly of dispersion forces or weak dipole-dipole interaction making a positive contribution, (2) chemical or specific interactions, which include charge transfer, forming of H-bonds and other complex forming interactions, resulting in a negative contribution and (3) structural contribution due to differences in size and shape of the component molecules of the mixtures, due to fitting of component molecules into each other's structure, hereby reducing the volume and compressibility of the mixtures, resulting in a negative contribution.

The large positive V_m^E values (Fig. 1) for *n* of *n*-decane with hexan-2-ol, heptan-2-ol and octan-2-ol mixture are attributed to the breaking up of three-dimensional H-bonded network of alkane-2-ol due to the addition of solute, which is not compensated by the weak interactions between unlike molecules. The V_m^E values

for binary mixtures of *n*-decane with alkane-2-ol are in the order : octan-2-ol > heptan-2-ol > hexan-2-ol.

Fig. 2 depicts the variation of $\Delta\eta$ with mole fraction of the binary mixtures of *n*-decane with hexan-2-ol, heptan-2-ol and octan-2-ol with at $T = 298.15$ K, shows negative deviation over the entire composition range.

Fig. 2. Plot of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) against mole fraction of *n*-decane with (O) hexane-2-ol; (□) heptane-2-ol and octane-2-ol (Δ) at $T = 298.15$ K.

The deviations viscosity may be generally explained²² by considering following factors : (1) the difference in size and shape of the component molecules and the loss of dipolar association to a decrease in viscosity and (2) specific interactions between unlike molecules such as H-bond formation and charge transfer complexes may cause for the increase in viscosity in mixtures rather than in pure component. The former effect produces negative in excess viscosity and latter effect produces positive in excess viscosity. Positive values of $\Delta\eta$ are indicative of strong interactions whereas negative values indicate weaker interactions²³.

The negative deviations in viscosity support the main factor of breaking of the self-associated alcohols and weak interactions between unlike molecules, decrease systematically with an increased in chain length of alkan-2-ol. With increasing in chain length of alcohols, hydrogen bonding interaction of *n*-decane with alkanols is weaker due to decreased polarizability. The negative values vis-

cosity deviation decreases in the following sequence :
hexan-2-ol > heptan-2-ol > octan-2-ol.

Theoretical analysis :

Semi-empirical models for analyzing viscosity of liquid mixtures :

Several empirical and semi-empirical relations have been used to represent the dependence of viscosity on concentration of components in binary liquid mixtures and these are classified according to the number of adjustable parameters used to account for the deviation from some average^{24;25}. We will consider here some of the most commonly used semi-empirical models for analyzing viscosity of liquid mixtures based on one, two and three parameters. An attempt has been made to check the suitability of equations for experimental data fits by taking into account the number of empirical adjustment coefficients.

The equation of Grunberg-Nissan, Tamara and Kurata Hind *et al.* and Katti and Chaudhari has one adjustable parameter.

Grunberg-Nissan provided the following empirical equation containing one adjustable parameter²⁶. The equation is

$$\ln \eta_{12} = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 G_{12} \quad (6)$$

where G_{12} may be regarded as a parameter proportional to the interchange energy also an approximate measure of the strength of the interaction between the components.

The one-parameter equation due to Tamura and Kurata²⁷ is gave the equation of the form

$$\eta_m = x_1 \eta_1 \Phi_1 + x_2 \eta_2 \Phi_2 + 2(x_1 x_2 \Phi_1 \Phi_2)^{1/2} T_{12} \quad (7)$$

where Φ_1 and Φ_2 are the volume fractions of components 1 and 2, respectively; T_{12} is Tamura and Kurata constant.

Hind *et al.*²⁸ proposed the following equation

$$\eta_m = x_1^2 \eta_1 + x_2^2 \eta_2 + 2x_1 x_2 H_{12} \quad (8)$$

where H_{12} is attributed to unlike pair interactions.

Katti and Chaudhari²⁹ derived the following equation

$$\ln \eta V = x_1 \ln \eta V_1^0 + x_2 \ln \eta V_2^0 + x_1 x_2 W_{\text{vis}}/RT \quad (9)$$

where W_{vis} is an interaction term and V_i^0 is the molar volume of pure component *i*.

Heric³⁰ expression is

$$\ln \eta_m = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + \ln (x_1 \eta_1 + x_2 \eta_2) + \delta_{12} \quad (10)$$

where $\delta_{12} = \alpha_{12} x_1 x_2$ is a term representing departure from a non-interacting system and $\alpha_{12} = \alpha_{21}$ is the interaction parameter. Either α_{12} or α_{21} can be expressed as a linear function of composition :

$$\alpha_{12} = \beta'_{12} + \beta''_{12} (x_1 - x_2) \quad (11)$$

From an initial guess of the values of coefficients β'_{12} and β''_{12} the values of α_{12} are computed.

Heric and Brewer³¹ equation is

$$\ln v = x_1 \ln v_1 + x_2 \ln v_2 + x_1 \ln M_1 + x_2 \ln M_2 - \ln [x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2] + x_1 x_2 [\alpha_{12} + \alpha_{21} (x_1 - x_2)] \quad (12)$$

M_1 and M_2 are molecular weights of components 1 and 2 and α_{12} and α_{21} are interaction parameters and other terms involved have their usual meaning. α_{12} and α_{21} are parameters, which can be calculated from the least-squares method.

McAllister's multibody interaction model³² was widely used to correlate kinematic viscosity (v) data. The two-parameter McAllister equation based on Eyring's³³ theory of absolute reaction rates taken into account interaction of both like and unlike molecules by two dimensional three-body model. The three-body interaction model is

$$\ln v_m = x_1^3 \ln v_1 + 3x_1^2 x_2 \ln Z_{12} + 3x_1 x_2^2 \ln Z_{21} + x_2^3 \ln v_2 - \ln [x_1 + (x_2 M_2)/M_1] + 3x_1^2 x_2 \ln [2/3 + M_2/(3M_1)] + 3x_1 x_2^2 \ln [1/3 + 2M_2/(3M_1)] x_2^3 \ln (M_2/M_1) \quad (13)$$

and four body model was given by

$$\ln v_m = x_1^4 \ln v_1 + 4x_1^3 x_2 \ln Z_{1112} + 6x_1^2 x_2^2 \ln Z_{1122} + 4x_1 x_2^3 \ln Z_{2221} + x_2^4 \ln v_2 - \ln [x_1 + x_2 (M_2/M_1)] + 4x_1^3 x_2 \ln [3 + (M_2/M_1)/4] + 6x_1^2 x_2^2 \ln [1 + (M_2/M_1)/2] + 4x_1 x_2^3 \ln [1 + (3M_2/M_1)/4] + x_2^4 \ln (M_2/M_1) \quad (14)$$

where Z_{12} , Z_{21} , Z_{1112} , Z_{1122} and Z_{2221} are interaction parameters and M_i and v_i are the molecular mass and kinematic viscosity of pure component *i*, respectively.

The correlating ability of each of eqs. (6)–(14) was tested and their adjustable parameters and standard deviations (σ) :

$$\sigma (\%) =$$

$$[(1/(n - k)\sum 100(\eta_{\text{exptl}} - \eta_{\text{calcd}})/\eta_{\text{exptl}})^2]^{1/2} \quad (15)$$

where n represents the number of data points and k is the

Table 3. Coefficients a_i of eq. (5) and corresponding standard deviation (σ) of eq. (6) at $T = 298.15$ K

System	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	σ
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + hexane-2-ol (2)					
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	2.033	0.152	-0.5406	1.9	0.007
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-5.658	2.011	0.884	-2.605	0.022
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + heptan-2-ol (2)					
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	1.61	0.062	-0.443	0.276	0.001
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-8.242	2.446	2.906	-3.59	0.052
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + octan-2-ol (2)					
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	1.129	0.1677	-0.462	0.1437	0.0023
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-8.4704	2.2136	-6.8274	-1.0134	0.1273

Table 4. Adjustable parameters of eqs. (7)–(14) and standard deviations of binary mixture viscosities for x_1 *n*-decane + (1 - x_1) alkane-2-ol at $T = 298.15$ K

Equation	System including <i>n</i> -decane + alkane-2-ol		
	Hexane-2-ol	Heptane-2-ol	Octane-2-ol
Grunberg-Nissan			
G_{12}	-2.253	-3.724	-3.226
σ	1.124	3.597	3.904
Tamura and Kurata			
T_{12}	0.005	-0.925	-1.117
σ	0.355	1.766	1.884
Hind <i>et al.</i>			
H_{12}	-3.75	-1.266	-1.409
σ	0.964	1.956	1.145
Katti and Chaudhari			
W_{vis}	-2.173	-3.665	-3.198
σ	1.134	3.602	3.905
Herc and Brewer			
α_{12}	-2.26	-4.248	-3.936
α_{21}	-2.912	-5.406	-5.529
σ	0.461	2.001	2.449
McAllister's three-body			
Z_{12}	0.467	0.081	0.094
Z_{21}	2.272	5.225	7.068
σ	0.463	2.03	2.449
McAllister's four-body			
Z_{1112}	0.481	0.059	0.511
Z_{1122}	2.157	8.543	1.897
Z_{2221}	2.591	1.976	1.998
σ	0.325	0.397	1.865

number of numerical coefficients are given in Table 4. The interaction parameter G_{12} is negative for binary systems. Nigam and Mahl²⁸ concluded from the study of binary mixtures that; (1) if $\Delta\eta > 0$, $G_{12} > 0$ and magnitude of both are large then strong specific interaction would be present, (2) if $\Delta\eta < 0$, $G_{12} > 0$ then weak specific interaction would be present and (3) if $\Delta\eta < 0$, $G_{12} < 0$ magnitude of both are large then the dispersion force would be dominant. According to Fort and Moore²⁹ and Ramamoorthy³⁰, system exhibits strong interaction if the G_{12} is positive; if it is negative they show weak interaction. On this basis we can say that there is weak interaction in the system studied.

Interaction parameter W_{vis} shows almost same trend as that of G_{12} . In fact one could say that the parameter G_{12} and W_{vis} exhibit almost similar behaviour, which is not unlikely in view of logarithmic nature of both equation.

Tamura and Kurata and Hind *et al.* represent the binary mixture satisfactory as compared to Grunberg-Nissan and Katti and Chaudhari use of three parameters equation reduces the σ values significantly below that of two parameters equation. From this study it can be concluded that the correlating ability significantly improves for these non ideal systems as number of adjustable parameter is increased. From Table 4, it is clear that McAllister's three-body interaction model is suitable for correlating the kinematic viscosities of the binary mixtures studied.

Prigogine-Flory-Patterson (PFP) theory :

The Prigogine-Flory-Patterson (PFP) theory³⁴⁻³⁷ has been commonly employed to estimate and analyze excess thermodynamic functions theoretically. This theory has been described in details by Patterson and co-workers^{38,39}. According to PFP theory, V_m^E can be separated into three factors : (1) an interactional contribution, V_m^E (int), (2) a free volume contribution, V_m^E (f_v) and (3) an internal pressure contribution, V_m^E (P^*). The expression for these three contributions are given as V_m^E

$$V_m^E \text{ (int)} = [(\tilde{v}^{1/3} - 1) \tilde{v}^{2/3} \psi_1 \theta_2 / (4/3 \tilde{v}^{-1/3} - 1) P_1^* \chi_{12}] \quad (16)$$

$$V_m^E (f_v) = [\tilde{v}_1 - \tilde{v}_2]^2 / (14/9 \tilde{v}^{-1/3} - 1) \psi_1 \psi_2 / [(14/9 \tilde{v}^{-1/3} - 1) \tilde{v}] \quad (17)$$

$$V_m^E (P^*) = [(\tilde{v}_1 - \tilde{v}_2) (P_1^* + P_2^*) \psi_1 \psi_2] / (P_1^* \psi_1 + P_2^* \psi_2) \quad (18)$$

Thus, the excess molar volume V_m^E is given as

$$V_m^E/(x_1V_1 + x_2V_2) = V_m^E(\text{int}) - V_m^E(f_v) + V_m^E(P^*) \quad (19)$$

where ψ , θ and P^* represent the contact energy fraction, surface site fraction, and characteristic pressure, respectively, and are calculated as

$$\psi_1 = (1 - \psi_2) = \Phi_1 P_1^*/(\Phi_1 P_1^* + \Phi_2 P_2^*) \quad (20)$$

$$\theta_2 = (1 - \theta_1) = \Phi_2/[\Phi_1(V_2^*/V_1^*)] \quad (21)$$

$$P^* = T \tilde{v}^2 \alpha \quad (22)$$

The details of the notations and terms used in eqs. (16)–(21) may be obtained from the literature^{34–37,40,41}. The other parameters pertaining to pure liquids and the mixtures are obtained from the Flory theory^{34,41,42} while α and κ_T values are taken from the literature^{43,44–49}. These values are reported in Table 4. The interaction parameter χ_{12} required for the calculation of V_m^E using PFP theory has been derived by fitting the V_m^E expression to the experimental equimolar value of V_m^E for each system under study.

The values of χ_{12} , θ_2 , three PFP contributions interactional, free volume, and P^* effect, and experimental and calculated (using PFP theory) V_m^E values at near equimolar composition are presented in Table 5. Study of the data presented in Table 5 reveals that the interactional and free volume contributions are positive, whereas P^* contributions are negative for all the three systems under investigation. For these binary mixtures, it is only the interactional contribution which dominates over the remaining two contributions. The P^* contribution, which depends both on the differences of internal pressures and differences of reduced volumes of the components, has little significance for the studied binary mixtures as compared to other two.

Furthermore, in order to check whether χ_{12} , derived from nearly equimolar V_m^E values can predict the correct composition dependence, V_m^E has been calculated theo-

retically using χ_{12} over the entire composition range. The theoretically calculated values are plotted in Fig. 1 for comparison with the experimental results. Fig. 1 show that the PFP theory is quite successful in predicting the trend of the dependence of V_m^E on composition for the present systems.

In order to perform a numerical comparison of the estimation capability of the PFP theory, we calculated the standard percentage deviations ($\sigma\%$) using the relation

$$\sigma\% = [\Sigma\{100(\text{Expt} - \text{Theor})/\text{Expt}\}(n - 1)]^{1/2} \quad (23)$$

where n represents the number of experimental data points. The values of $\sigma\%$ are also given in Table 5.

Bloomfield and Dewan model :

There are different expressions available in the literature to calculate η . Here, Bloomfield and Dewan⁵⁰ model have been applied to compare calculated $\Delta \ln \eta$ values using experimental data for each binary mixture by the following relation

$$\Delta \ln \eta = \ln \eta - (x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2) \quad (24)$$

Bloomfield and Dewan⁵⁰ developed the expression from the combination of the theories of free volumes and absolute reaction rate

$$\Delta \ln \eta = f(\tilde{v}) - \Delta G^R/RT \quad (25)$$

where $f(\tilde{v})$ is the characteristic function of the free volume defined

$$f(\tilde{v}) = 1/(\tilde{v} - 1)x_1/(\tilde{v}_1 - 1) - x_2/(\tilde{v}_2 - 1) \quad (26)$$

and ΔG^R is the residual energy of mixing, calculated with the following expression⁵⁰ :

$$\Delta G^R = \Delta G^E - RT\{x_1 \ln(x_1/\Phi_1) + x_2 \ln(x_2/\Phi_2)\} \quad (27)$$

where Φ_1 and Φ_2 are segment fraction defined by

$$\Phi_2 = 1 - \Phi_1 = x_2/[x_2 + x_1(r_1/r_2)] \quad (28)$$

where r_1 and r_2 are in the ratio of respective molar core volumes V_1^* and V_2^* .

The excess energy can be obtained from the statistical theory of liquid mixtures proposed by Flory and coworkers^{31,32} and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^E = & x_1 P_1^* V_1^* [1/(\tilde{v}_1) - 1/(\tilde{v}) \\ & + 3\tilde{T}_1 \ln \{(\tilde{v}_1^{1/3} - 1)/(\tilde{v}^{1/3} - 1)\} \\ & + x_2 P_2^* V_2^* [1/(\tilde{v}_2) - 1/(\tilde{v}) \\ & + \{3\tilde{T}_2 \ln \{(\tilde{v}_2^{1/3} - 1)/(\tilde{v}^{1/3} - 1)\} \\ & + (x_1 \theta_2 V_1^* \chi_{12})/\tilde{v} \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Table 5. Flory parameters of the pure compounds at $T = 298.15$ K

Components	$10^6 V^*$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$10^6 P^*$ (J m^{-3})	T^* (K)
<i>n</i> -Decane	155.6091	453	5091
Hexane-2-ol	102.532	476	5517
Heptane-2-ol	115.600	512	5415
Octan-2-ol	129.9790	535	5563

where the various symbols used have their usual meanings.

Using the χ_{12} values from fitting values of V_m^E and the values of the parameters for the pure liquid components, we have calculated, ΔG^R and $f(\bar{v})$ and finally $\Delta \ln \eta$, according to the Bloomfield and Dewan relationship, which is compared with the experimental data (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Plot of $\Delta \ln \eta$ against mole fraction of *n*-decane with (○) hexane-2-ol; (□) heptane-2-ol and octane-2-ol (Δ) at $T = 298.15$ K. The corresponding dotted (---) curves have been derived from Bloomfield and Dewan model.

Fig. 3 shows that the good agreement between the estimated and experimental curves occurs for given binary system.

Jouyban and Acree model :

Hasan *et al.*^{7,51-53} has used this model for various binary systems.

The Jouyban-Acree model^{53,54} was introduced to correlate the physicochemical properties of the solution in mixed solvents including the dielectric constants, viscosity, solvatochromic parameter, and density, speed of sound and more recently molar volumes. The model uses the physicochemical properties of the mono-solvents as input data and a number of curve-fitting parameters representing the effects of solvent-solvent interactions in the solution. It is basically derived for representing the solvent effects on the solubility of non-polar solutes in nearly ideal binary solvent mixtures at isothermal conditions. The proposed equation is

$$\ln y_{m,T} = f_1 \ln y_{1,T} + f_2 \ln y_{2,T} + f_1 f_2 \sum [A_j (f_1 - f_2)^j / T] \quad (30)$$

where $y_{m,T}$, $y_{1,T}$ and $y_{2,T}$ is density, or viscosity of the mixture and solvents 1 and 2 at temperature T , respectively, f_1 and f_2 are the volume fractions of solvents in case of density, and mole fraction in case of viscosity, and A_j are the model constants.

Table 6. Calculated values of the three contributions to the excess molar volume from the PFP theory with interaction parameter at $T = 298.15$ K

Component	$\chi_{12} \times 10^6$ (J m ⁻³)	$V^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)		Calcd. contribution		
		at $x = 0.5$		$V^E \times 10^6$	$V^E \times 10^6$	$V^E \times 10^6$
		Expt.	PEP	(int)	(f_v)	(P^*)
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + hexane-2-ol (2)	19.36	0.499	0.498	0.596	0.042	-0.055
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + heptan-2-ol (2)	17.75	0.401	0.398	0.537	0.025	-0.109
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + octan-2-ol (2)	12.57	0.326	0.328	0.5999	0.0544	-0.2183

Table 7. Parameters of Jouyban-Acree model and average percentage deviation for densities, viscosities and ultrasonic velocities of binary mixtures at $T = 298.15$ K

System	A_0	A_1	A_2	APD
Density				
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + hexane-2-ol (2)	-16.812	1.275	-4.12	0.175
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + heptan-2-ol (2)	-11.498	2.104	-1.91	0.154
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + octan-2-ol (2)	-9.0926	1.0266	0.6448	0.1183
Viscosity				
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + hexane-2-ol (2)	-5.123	9.236	-3.125	0.812
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + heptan-2-ol (2)	-6.321	8.123	-2.158	0.913
<i>n</i> -Decane (1) + octan-2-ol (2)	-4.2926	11.2857	-2.7614	0.7668

The correlating ability of the Jouyban-Acree model was tested by calculating the average percentage deviation (APD) between the experimental and calculated density and viscosity as

$$APD = (100/N) \sum [(|y_{\text{exptl}} - y_{\text{calcd}}|)/y_{\text{exptl}}] \quad (31)$$

where *N* is the number of data points in each set. The optimum numbers of constants *A_j*, in each case, were determined from the examination of the average percentage deviation value.

The constants *A_j* calculated from the least square analysis are presented in Table 6 along with the average percentage deviation (APD). The proposed model provides reasonably accurate calculations for the density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity of binary liquid mixtures at 298.15 K and the model could be used in data modeling. One representative system for experimental and calculated density, and viscosity of binary liquid mixture of *n*-dodecane with 2-octanol at 298.15 K using Jouyban-Acree model is given in Table 7.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Principal Dr. R. S. Agarwal, J. E. S. College, Jalna for the facilities provided.

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